

Reconstructing dust provenance from quartz optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) and electron spin resonance (ESR) signals: Preliminary results on loess from around the world

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Abstract

Quantitative provenance analysis studies are instrumental in understanding the tectonic and climatic processes that shape the earth's landscape. Although the most abundant mineral in the sedimentary system is quartz, almost all studies in provenance analysis investigate accessory minerals. Quartz crystals contain a vast number of point defects, intrinsic or due to impurities. For a signal to be an accurate indicator of provenance one needs to show that it is either dose independent or reaches a quantifiable steady state characteristic of the source rock. For signals used by trapped charge dating methods (optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) and electron spin resonance (ESR)), the latter option is the feasible one. By using quartz samples collected from the Chinese Loess Plateau (Luochuan loess-paleosol section), we show that the laboratory and natural dose response curves of E'_{1} and peroxy electron spin resonance signals of quartz (as defined later) overlap and reach a steady state for doses over about 1000 Gy. For E'_{1} signals we attribute this steady state to reaching an equilibrium state between diamagnetic oxygen vacancies (the oxygen deficiency centre (ODC), Si=Si) and paramagnetic oxygen vacancies (E'_{1}). For sedimentary quartz irradiated naturally or artificially in this dose range we show a strong linear relationship with zero intercept between E'_{1} and peroxy signals for samples worldwide, supporting the hypothesis that these defects are Frenkel pairs. Further, we show significant correlations between the optically stimulated (OSL) sensitivity and the above two mentioned ESR signals. The very strong correlations (Pearson's $r > 0.9$) between E'_{1} , peroxy and OSL sensitivity remain valid after the samples have been heated for 15 min to 350 °C for E'_{1} to reach its maximum value, believed to be a result of the conversion of diamagnetic oxygen vacancies to E'_{1} ,

clearly suggesting a relationship between OSL sensitivity and oxygen vacancies in general. Samples collected from different loess sites around the world can be distinguished based on both these OSL and ESR properties. An empirical increase in OSL sensitivity as well as oxygen related defect concentrations is observed in areas where the source material has components with older detrital zircon U-Pb ages, inferring a positive correlation between OSL sensitivity, as well as the signal intensity for E_1' and peroxy defects and the age of the source rocks.

Keywords: quartz, oxygen-related point defects, ESR, OSL, provenance

Highlights

- Natural dose response curves of E_1' and peroxy ESR signals in quartz overlap and reach steady state.
- Strong linear relationship with zero intercept between E_1' and peroxy signals.
- Significant correlations between the optically stimulated (OSL) sensitivity and E_1' and peroxy signals.
- Quartz derived from loess samples from different locations around the world can be distinguished based on OSL and ESR properties.

1. Introduction

The sediment routing concept (Allen, 2008) tries to conceptually integrate tectonic fluxes and climatically driven erosion, an approach that is at the core of modern studies on Earth surface processes. The concept relies on the potential to track individual mineral grains from their source to their sinks. Provenance studies are instrumental in this respect. Durability and abundance of quartz ensures that parent rocks containing quartz are represented by detrital quartz in their daughter sediment (Basu, 1985). Quartz deserves a principal focus in quantitative provenance studies. However, quartz is considered a pure mineral that does not carry much information about its origin and almost all studies in provenance analysis utilise accessory minerals, zircon being the gold standard. As such the primary mineral in sands is not analysed, precluding quantitative analysis.

Natural Quartz crystals contain a vast number of point defects, which may be either intrinsic (e.g., O-vacancies and related defects or Si vacancies) or due to impurities, most often as combination of

monovalent (H^+ , Li^+ , and Na^+) and trivalent (Al^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , and B^{3+}) cations (e.g., Götze, 2009, Preusser et al., 2009). Some of these defects remain unchanged under ionizing radiation bombardment by the omnipresent natural radioactivity, while others are being transformed. Some of these defects are diamagnetic (such as the oxygen deficiency centre (ODC, $Si=Si$), $[AlO_4/M^+]^0$ (generally denoted as Al-M) where M^+ could be Li^+ , Na^+ or K^+ , or Al compensated with hydrogen ions $[AlO_4/H^+]^0$ (denoted as Al-H) or the peroxy linkages ($Si-O-O-Si$). Other defects are paramagnetic and thus can be identified by electron spin resonance measurements (e.g. E'_{1} , an unpaired electron at an oxygen vacancy site ($\equiv Si\cdot$), peroxy intrinsic defect centers ($\equiv Si-O-O\cdot$), nonbridging oxygen NBOHC, ($\equiv Si-O\cdot$), Al related paramagnetic defects such as Al-hole ($[AlO_4]^0$), titanium impurity defects such as $[TiO_4/Li^+]^0$ or $[TiO_4/H^+]^0$, germanium defects such as $[GeO_4]^0$ or $[GeO_4/M^+]$ where M^+ is a cation, and so on (e.g. Weil, 2000, Mashkovtsev and Pan, 2013)) while others have the ability to emit light upon stimulation. Based on the dynamics of these radiation sensitive defects under irradiation, quartz can record the amount of ionising radiation it has been exposed to since a resetting event. These signals can be excited and quantified by controlled heating or light exposure as well as by subjecting the sample to a magnetic and microwave field. As such, quartz is used for dating sediments by thermoluminescence (TL) or optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) (Aitken, 1985; 1998) as well as by electron spin resonance (ESR) (Ikeya, 1993) using generally Al and Ti related defects (e.g. Duval et al., 2017). These methods date the event when sediment was last exposed to heat or light, consequently resetting the signal to zero. The underlying assumption of these methods is that signal growth in nature as a result of exposure to natural radioactivity can be reproduced by performing laboratory irradiations.

In contrast to signals used for dating (e.g. OSL, TL, Al and Ti related paramagnetic defects) increase with dose (and hence with time) for most if not all sedimentary quartz specimens, the rate of increase (sensitivity) is well known to be sample dependent. The sensitivity of OSL is defined as the amount of the signal emitted per unit of radiation dose (Gy) for a defined unit of mass of the sample. Due to the nature of the protocols used (Murray and Wintle 2000, 2003) sensitivity itself is not routinely quantified in luminescence dating. However, it is well known that some samples cannot be dated because of their low signals. Low luminescence sensitivity has been reported for quartz from several parts of the world, particularly where the quartz grains have only recently been released from the source rock of young ages such as the European Alps or the New Zealand Alps (see Preusser et al., 2009 and the references cited therein). In most luminescence dating studies, it is implicitly or explicitly assumed that transport history is the main factor increasing the sensitivity (Preusser et al., 2006, Moska et al., 2006, Pietsch et al., 2008, Tsukamoto et al., 2011). However, we have been unable to sensitise OSL signals of quartz extracted from New Zealand loess, which most likely derives from the young

New Zealand Alps, by laboratory bleaching and irradiation (Brezeanu et al., 2021). Quartz luminescence sensitivity was proposed as a parameter that can reflect the source variation for the sediments (Sawakuchi et al., 2012, 2018). However, it is debated whether quartz OSL sensitisation is induced by Earth surface processes (e.g. Sawakuchi et al., 2011) or driven by the intrinsic properties of crystals in the source rock, as shown by recent studies (e.g. Capaldi et al., 2022, Alexanderson, 2022). Moreover, there is no proper explanation of the variability of luminescence sensitivity (by up to ten orders of magnitude) between samples. It is reasonable to assume that luminescence sensitivity of quartz in sediments is controlled by a variety of factors (Fitzsimmons, 2011) which besides sedimentary history includes the nature and the concentration of intrinsic as well as impurity defects in quartz determined by the physical, chemical, and the thermal environments during crystallization, as well as the age of the host rock.

On the other hand, intrinsic, oxygen related defects in quartz that can be quantified by electron spin resonance (ESR), such as the concentration of paramagnetic oxygen vacancies in the form of the E' native defect (Rink and Odom, 1991, Dave et al., 2022a) or the heat-treated E'1, thought to reflect the total number of oxygen vacancies (Toyoda and Hattori, 2000, Toyoda, 2005, Toyoda et al., 2016), and peroxy signals (Rink and Odom, 1991, Dave et al., 2022a) have been shown to correlate with the age of rocks and have been proposed as provenance indicators.

The term peroxy signals (or sometimes peroxy signal) commonly used in the literature, refers to a number of overlapping signals observed in the range of g-factor values 2.01 - 1.99 (with the exception of E' and Ge centres) in ESR spectra of quartz recorded at room temperature (when the Al-h is not detectable). After first being established in neutron or gamma-ray irradiated ¹⁷O-enriched fused silica (Friebele et al., 1979), peroxy radicals in crystalline SiO₂ (α-quartz) have been investigated in detail by Botis et al. (Botis et al., 2005, 2008), Nilges et al. (Nilges et al., 2009, 2008), and Pan et al. (Pan et al., 2009, 2008, Pan and Hu, 2009). Despite the wealth of information provided by these studies, there are still many unanswered questions regarding the nature of these signals. Over 20 different species have been identified so far, characterised often by very slight differences in g-factor values, and sometimes complex signals arising due to hyperfine interactions. The spectrum resulting from the superposition of these signals is impossible to resolve without the aid of higher microwave frequencies (Q-band or W-band). For simplicity, in this study, as in the previous studies conducted by our group (Dave et al., 2022, Kabacińska and Timar-Gabor, 2022), we use the term “peroxy” to describe all the signals observed in the aforementioned range (except E' and Ge). It should be noted, that by this

definition any signals related to the non-bridging oxygen hole centre (NBOHC), would also be included.

Here, we work towards obtaining a better understanding of the relationship between intrinsic defects in quartz that can be quantified by ESR and luminescence properties such as the OSL sensitivity, with the final aim of establishing a trapped charge quartz-based provenance method. The advantages of these physical methods compared to the analysis of trace elements in quartz (e.g., Ackerson et al., 2015) is that they have dynamic properties and thus has the potential to discriminate not only between rocks of different compositions but also between rocks of different ages. We analyse quartz extracted from loess sites from different locations around the world, from which detrital zircon U-Pb age distributions have been previously presented. The advantage of using loess is that it is windblown and transported over long distances. Thus, it can be assumed that the intrinsic characteristics of the source rocks can be distinguished over the effect of transport in the variability of the luminescence and ESR properties of sedimentary quartz grains.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Samples

Luminescence analyses were performed on archived quartz extracts used in previous OSL and ESR dating studies. Samples from the Chinese Loess Plateau (Luochuan) on which natural and laboratory dose response curves of E'_1 and peroxy signals are presented (section 3.1) are the same samples previously used by Kabacińska et al., 2022. The depositional age spans from Holocene (expected age of 1 ka and equivalent dose of about 3 Gy) to the Tertiary-Quaternary boundary (expected age of about 2.5 Ma and equivalent dose of about 7.5 kGy). Sample END 1.2. is collected from Enders loess site in Nebraska and its depositional age was dated by OSL to 2.2 ka (equivalent dose of 8.2 Gy) by Tecsá et al., 2020. The OSL signal of sample STY 1.10 from North Ukraine was found close to saturation and its properties were described in detail by Veres et al., 2018. Samples from South Ukraine were collected from the Roxolany site. For both samples the OSL signal was found close to saturation and sample ROX 1.14 was dated by ESR using Al-hole and Ti signals to an age higher than 1000 ka (equivalent doses of more than 2000 Gy) by Anechitei-Deacu et al., 2018. Sample HUG comes from Dunaszekcső loess sequence in Hungary, Carpathian Basin, and has a depositional age of about 40 ka (Újvári et al., 2014). Samples coded as 2MV were collected from Mircea Voda loess-paleosol site in Romania. Sample 2MV80 was dated to 15.5 ka and equivalent dose of 36.4 Gy, while the OSL signal

of sample 2MVL3A was found close to saturation (Groza-Săcaciuc et al., 2020). The location of all samples presented in this study are shown in a map in **figure S1**.

For the analysis carried out in sections 3.2., 3.3. and 3.4, as explained below, in the case of samples with a depositional age of less than 1000 Gy we have used material available from our laboratory archive that was gamma irradiated on top of the doses acquired during deposition. Therefore, sample HUG was irradiated with 2000 Gy, sample 2MV80 was irradiated with doses of 2000 and 5000 Gy respectively, sample 2MVL3A with a dose of 2000 Gy, sample END 1.2 was irradiated with a dose of 4000 Gy while sample STY 1.10 was irradiated with a dose of 2000 Gy. It should be noted that all samples used in these latter sections are pure loess sample and not samples collected from paleosols, as an increase in the OSL sensitivity of quartz in paleosols with a not yet known explanation was previously reported (e.g., Lü et al., 2014, Dave et al., 2022b). The choice of the samples used was further dictated by the following factors: their purity (in terms of lack of contamination of the quartz extracts with other minerals), the aim to cover a geographical/geological realm as vast as possible and lastly, by the availability of a significant amount of material.

2.2. Sample preparation

The quartz extraction was performed under low intensity red light. Bulk sediment samples were treated with hydrochloric acid (HCl, 10% concentration) for calcium carbonate removal, followed by hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂, 30% concentration) treatment for organic matter removal. The 63-90 µm fraction was separated by wet sieving. A two-step density separation centrifugation 2.62 g/cm³ and 2.75 g/cm³, respectively using heavy liquids (sodium metatungstate (Na₆[H₂W₁₂O₃₉] x H₂O)) was performed to extract the 63-90 µm quartz grains. Further etching with 40% hydrofluoric acid (HF) for 40 minutes was performed. The fluorides that precipitated following the HF attack were washed away following a 60 minute bath in 10% HCl. For luminescence measurements, the 63-90 µm quartz grains were mounted as monolayer on 9-mm diameter stainless steel disks with silicon oil used as adhesive. For ESR measurements samples were placed in quartz glass tubes filled by maintaining the same height (2 cm), with a mass 192 ± 2 mg (larger tubes with an inner diameter of 4 mm) for the samples used to construct the Luochuan natural and laboratory dose response curves (see section 3.1) and 81 ± 10 mg for the rest of the samples (smaller tubes with an inner diameter of 2 mm) (sections 3.2, 3.3.,3.4). For ESR measurements data was normalized to 100 mg for inter-comparison.

2.3. Analytical facilities and measurement protocols

Luminescence measurements were carried out using TL/OSL Risø DA-20 readers equipped automated detection and stimulation head (DASH) (Lapp et al., 2015). The luminescence signals were stimulated using blue LEDs (470 nm, $\sim 80 \text{ mW/cm}^2$) and detected through 7.5 mm thick Hoya U-340 filters placed in front of a PDM 9107Q-AP-TTL-03 photomultiplier. Irradiations were performed using built-in $^{90}\text{Sr}/^{90}\text{Y}$ (beta irradiation) source calibrated using calibration quartz provided by the Nordic Laboratory for Luminescence Dating. The optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) of 63-90 μm quartz was measured using a Single Aliquot Regenerative dose (SAR) protocol (Murray and Wintle 2000, Murray and Wintle 2003) given in **table S1**. The OSL sensitivity was evaluated as the net OSL signal induced by the first 17 Gy test dose. The luminescence signal was stimulated with blue LEDs for 40 s at 125 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the net signal was isolated from the first 0.308 s of luminescence emission minus a background assessed from the 1.538–2.307 s of luminescence emission (**figure S2**).

ESR measurements were performed on an X band Bruker EMX Plus spectrometer. Each sample was measured 3 times and rotated in the cavity between the measurements. Exposure of samples to sunlight during measurements was restricted to a minimum. Measurements were carried out at room temperature for E'_{1} and peroxy centres. Peroxy spectra were acquired using the following settings: $3350 \pm 200 \text{ G}$ scanned magnetic field, modulation amplitude 1 G, modulation frequency 100 kHz, microwave power 2 mW, conversion time 50 ms, time constant 40 ms. For E'_{1} spectra the settings were: $3363 \pm 10 \text{ G}$ scanned magnetic field, modulation amplitude 0.1 G, modulation frequency 100 kHz, microwave power 0.02 mW, conversion time 30 ms, time constant 20.48 ms, and 3 scans per measurement. Baseline correction for peroxy spectra was performed using Bruker's Xenon software. The signal amplitude was determined from the peak-to-peak height from $g = 2.0004$ to $g = 2.0001$ for E'_{1} signal (uncertainty ± 0.0001) (**Figure S3 a**), and from $g = 2.0090$ to $g = 2.0030$ for peroxy signal (uncertainty ± 0.0010) (Odom and Rink, 1989; **Figure S3b**).

Gamma irradiations for ESR experiments were performed at room temperature at the Department of Health Technology (Medical Isotopes and Dosimetry Unit) at technical University of Denmark using a calibrated ^{60}Co gamma cell with a dose rate of 2 Gy/s (dose rate to water) at the time of irradiation. Dose rate to quartz was estimated to be 96% of dose rate to water based on Monte Carlo simulation considering the irradiation geometry used. Heating was performed by placing the samples in the oven set at 350 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 15 minutes as for our experimental setup we have previously shown that this is the thermal treatment that enhances the E'_{1} signal to its maximum value (Dave et al., 2022a).

3. Results and discussions

3.1. E₁' and peroxy natural and laboratory dose response curves

For a signal to be an accurate indicator of provenance one needs to show that it is either dose independent or reaches a quantifiable steady state characteristic of the source rock. As our goal is to use trapped charge dating methods, identifying signals that fulfil the latter scenario is reasonable. This can be achieved if the signal of interest follows a dose response curve in the host rock, reaching by dynamic equilibrium a constant level, which is assumed to be the case for most trapped charge dating signals, and then one can recreate the same constant level by carrying out controlled laboratory irradiation on the derived sediments. The best test of this assumption can be carried out by comparing natural dose response curves, that is obtained in a geological setting with continuous known ages and hence known natural irradiation doses, to dose response curves constructed in the laboratory by controlled artificial irradiation. In the sedimentary realm, loess-paleosol sequences that are continuous and span over the Quaternary constitute the best testing grounds for this assumption.

Quartz from the Chinese Loess Plateau has been previously used for comparing the natural and laboratory dose response curves by Chapot et al. (2012, 2016) in luminescence studies (optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) and thermally transferred optically stimulated luminescence (TT-OSL), respectively), and later by Tsukamoto et al. (2018) and Kabacińska et al. (2022) in ESR studies using Al and Ti paramagnetic related signals. These studies show that for the investigated signals the natural and laboratory dose response curves do not overlap in their region of saturation, as such the above-mentioned signals cannot be used accurately used for provenance under our outlined assumption. But, to our knowledge E₁' and peroxy ESR natural dose response curves have not yet been presented. Here we have carried out these investigations for the first time and **Figure 1** presents the comparison of natural and laboratory dose response curves of E₁' (**panel a**) and peroxy (**panel b**) ESR signals, using the exact same samples as in Kabacińska et al. (2022). Despite the scatter in data which is to be expected when one constructs natural dose response curves, above 1000 Gy the natural as well as the laboratory response reach a steady state and overlap for both signals.

For E₁' signals the laboratory dose response curves show the same pattern, namely a decrease up to approximately 1000 Gy that has been previously presented by Toyoda and Schwartz, (1997), Bartoll et al., (2002) and more recently by Benzid and Timar-Gabor (2021), Toyoda and Amimoto (2021) and Dave et al., (2022a). In a natural sample it is clear that both paramagnetic (E₁') as well as diamagnetic

oxygen vacancies (ODC-oxygen deficiency centre) exist (see e.g. Toyoda et al., 1996). It is also clear that in a natural sample both Al-hole as well as the diamagnetic Al defects compensated by cations (H^+ , Li^+ , and Na^+) exist as the latter is the natural form while the former is generally thought to be created by irradiation. Benzid and Timar-Gabor (2021) tentatively explained the shape of the dose response curves of E'_{1} based on the fact that during irradiation electrons are trapped by the E'_{1} that is transformed into the ODC, while at the same time the ODC traps holes transforming into E'_{1} until a dynamic equilibrium is reached, as seen in the case of our dataset for doses above 1000 Gy. We acknowledge that at this stage this is a simplistic view and other defects might act as competitors. For example, a correlation between Al-hole centre and E'_{1} by hole transfer from the former to the latter has been proposed under heating since the seminal work of Jani et al. (1983) as well as under light exposure by Benzid and Timar-Gabor (2021). By analysing dose response curves of E'_{1} signals for samples with different depositional ages, we observe that the decrease up to about 1000 Gy is more significant in the case of samples that accrued a lower dose since the bleaching. This means samples with lower depositional equivalent doses or in other words sediments that have recently bleached (see for example figure S2 in Dave et al., 2022a where dose response curves for E'_{1} signals of various loess samples with different equivalent doses from Central Asia, Danube Basin and Nebraska, USA are presented).

Indeed, right after light exposure one should expect an increase in E'_{1} signals due to hole transfer from Al-h to the ODC. As such, in depositionally young samples E'_{1} should have relatively high values. In case of Al related defects in depositionally young samples, the amount of Al-hole defects should be at a relative minimum value compared to the cation compensated form (Al-H, Al-M), since as it is widely accepted that Al-hole defects are bleachable. At the same time, it is well known that irradiation increases the Al-hole concentration. This is said to occur when irradiation causes Al cation compensated defects to trap holes, releasing cations and therefore transforming into Al-hole (see e.g., Benzid and Timar-Gabor 2020 and references therein). As such, Al-cation compensated defects may act as hole trapping competitors for the oxygen deficiency centre (ODC), resulting in a less efficient conversion of ODC to E'_{1} and hence leading to the observed decrease of E'_{1} . At the same time Ti defects are known to be electron traps. As such, they can compete for trapping electrons with E'_{1} defects. However, Al is by far the most important impurity in quartz (see e.g. Preusser et al., 2009), thus one can reasonably assume that the absolute number of Al related defects is higher than the number of ODC or Ti related defects, hence resulting in a drop in the dose response curve of E'_{1} . While we acknowledge that the mechanism is complex, the steady state achieved and the overlap between natural and laboratory dose response curves is clear.

Figure 1: Dose response curves constructed for E'_1 (a) and peroxy (b) signals in natural and laboratory irradiated samples from Luochuan (Chinese Loess Plateau). Total dose is the sum of the expected dose obtained by a sample in nature and the laboratory dose coming from additional artificial irradiation. The expected doses were estimated based on ages reported in Ding et al., 2002, and the average dose

rate of ~ 3 Gy/ka (Chapot et al., 2012), the full description of the samples used is presented in Kabacińska et al. (2022).

The peroxy signals are shown in the supplementary material (**Figure S4**). These signals are complex, representing the overlap of signatures from various defects, as mentioned in the introduction. As studies are underway to better understand these defects, at the moment we would like to refrain from providing a physical explanation for the observed shape of the dose response curve in terms of the increase up to 1000 Gy. Nonetheless, it is worth mentioning the plateau of these signals with doses above 1000 Gy, which was also reported for quartz in Central Asia (Dave et al., 2022a, figure S3).

We do acknowledge that many other defects can be at play, however, for practical purposes, the overlap between the natural and laboratory dose response curves as well as the steady state observed, that should have also been reached in the host rock (at least since a closure temperature was reached) is very encouraging, and fully achievable for the first time to our knowledge in the case of trapped charge dating signals.

In the following section, we test whether E'_1 and peroxy ESR signals can be used to differentiate samples from various locations around the world and examine their relationship with OSL properties.

3.2. Correlation between E'_1 and peroxy ESR signals and OSL sensitivity.

Signals similar to the peroxy signals were first reported in quartz by McMorris (1970) and interpreted as fossil damage, due to accumulation of lattice damaged caused by alpha irradiation. Such radiation damage was later confirmed experimentally by 4 MeV He^{2+} ions that are equivalent to natural alpha particles (Okumura et al., 2008). Odom and Rink (1989) and Rink and Odom (1991) have shown that in a suite of quartz samples of known ages the intensities of both E'_1 signals as well as peroxy radicals were correlated to the crystallisation age of the source rock and proposed that Frenkel pairs are produced at a slow rate but in a continuous manner in the host rock by knock-on reactions initiated by the recoil of alpha emitting nuclei. Dave et al., (2022a) concurred with this hypothesis. It should be mentioned that Toyoda et al. (1996) supported the idea that oxygen vacancies are created by external beta and gamma rays. However, in this approach a heat treatment was involved (see next section). However, a later study lead by the same author (Toyoda et al., 2006) supported the theory that alpha particle damage is largely responsible for oxygen vacancy production during natural irradiation of quartz over intervals of hundreds of millions of years.

In short, the hypothesis that we propose (based on results also presented by other studies such as (Fiegl et al, 1974; Hobbs and Pascucci, 1980, Jani et al, 1983; Odom and Rink, 1989) is the following. The recoil of alpha emitting nuclei and or alpha particle irradiation damage itself from alpha emitting trace elements in quartz can lead to oxygen displacement. This leads, initially to the creation of neutral oxygen vacancies (the oxygen deficiency centre ODC) and peroxy linkages (Si-O-O-Si), known to be the more stable forms of oxygen deficiency and oxygen excess centres in quartz and silica (e.g. Salh, 2011). Both these defects can trap holes that are abundant because of natural irradiation with beta and gamma rays transforming into the E'_1 centre and the peroxy intrinsic defect centre in the long time spent in the host rock during geological time and eventually reaching a steady state. We do acknowledge that this steady state should be reached after the rock reaches a closure temperature and this will be investigated in future studies. This hypothesis has significant implications for provenance, as due to the low efficiency of the oxygen displacement process most Frenkel pairs should have been formed in the host rock, as the time spent in the host rock even after reaching a closure temperature, as well as the contribution of alpha irradiation during that time should be significantly higher than in the sedimentary realm. Also, based on previous studies on the thermal stability of these signals (e.g. Toyoda and Ikea, 1991) and especially because of the overlap of natural and laboratory dose response curves (**figure 1**) it is clear that these signals are stable over the temperatures reached in the sedimentary realm. As such we see no argument against the assumption that the steady state reached by E'_1 and peroxy defects after a dose of about 1000 Gy in the sedimentary realm does coincide with steady state that is reached by the same signals in the source rock that was exhumed and reached a certain closure temperature.

Figure 2 presents the dependence of E'_1 signals as function of the peroxy signals for loess samples from various locations around the world, that were laboratory irradiated or have a depositional equivalent dose larger than 1000 Gy for the steady state to be reached as explained in the previous section. The correlation observed is very strong with a Pearson's r coefficient of 0.95, supporting the hypothesis that the two defects are indeed Frenkel pairs. Such a correlation was previously reported by Dave et al., (2022a) for quartz loess in Central Asia.

Figure 2: ESR intensity of E'_1 versus peroxy measured for samples from Nebraska (END 1.2 + 4000Gy), North Ukraine (STY 1.10 + 2000Gy), South Ukraine (average of ROX 1.9 and ROX 1.14), Carpathian Basin (HUG + 2000Gy), Lower Danube Basin (average of 2 MV 80 + 2000Gy, 2 MV 80 + 5000Gy, 2MVL3A + 2000Gy), and Chinese Loess Plateau (average of D881-26, D881-28, D881-30 with expected depositional equivalent doses of 1334 Gy, 1768 Gy and 2500 Gy, respectively (Kabacińska et al., 2022)).

In the dataset presented here, although the quartz samples come from various locations around the world the data can be well fitted with a linear function with zero intercept. This further supports the hypothesis that the defects are indeed Frenkel pairs. The slope has no physical meaning as the ESR measurement procedure is different for the two defects and the measured values do not represent absolute defect concentrations.

Figure 3 presents the OSL sensitivity of the same samples as function of the intensity of E'_1 and peroxy signals. As previously mentioned, the values of the slope and intercept have no physical values. However, there is a clear direct relationship between the OSL sensitivity as well the E'_1 (panel a) and peroxy signals (panel b). The correlation (Pearson's r coefficient of 0.85 and 0.97, respectively) clearly indicates that oxygen related defects are likely involved in OSL sensitisation although the exact mechanism and whether this sensitisation occurs during transport (see e.g. Williams et al., 2022) or is influenced by the host rock properties requires further investigations. Most importantly, it is clear that

trapped charge dating properties such as OSL sensitivity as well as the signatures of E'_1 and peroxy signals have great potential as provenance tools as the samples investigated from around the world are clearly discernible, as they do not overlap even within uncertainties (the single exception being the values of E'_1 for Chinese loess and South Ukraine samples where error bars are larger due to averaging a relatively small number of samples). Samples from North Ukraine have by far the brightest OSL signals as well as the highest E'_1 and peroxy signals, while samples from the Carpathian basin have the weakest signals as well as the lowest OSL sensitivity.

Figure 3: Geographical average of OSL sensitivity plotted against amplitude of E'_1 (a) and “peroxy” signals, respectively (b). The samples and their dosage used for each region are as follows: Nebraska: END 1.2 natural + 4000 Gy, North Ukraine: STY 1.10 + 2000 Gy, South Ukraine: ROX 1.9 natural, ROX 1.14 natural, Carpathian basin: HUG natural + 2000 Gy, Lower Danube basin: 2MV80 natural + 2000 Gy, 2MV80 natural + 5000 Gy, 2MVL3A natural + 2000 Gy, Chinese Loess: D881-26, D881-28, D881-30 with expected depositional equivalent doses of 1334 Gy, 1768 Gy and 2500 Gy, respectively (Kabacińska et al., 2022).

3.4. Heating experiments and correlation to the total number of oxygen vacancies

The increase of E'_1 with heating is known for decades (Jani et al., 1983). Toyoda et al. (1992) performed such a heat treatment on quartz from granites suggesting that the signal of heat treated E'_1 signal is a better indication of the number of vacancies. Based on this, Toyoda and co-workers (see Toyoda et al., 2016 and references therein) proposed using heat treated E'_1 as a provenance indicator, recommending a heat treatment (30 minutes at 430 °C), aimed at annealing the initial concentration of E'_1 centre, followed by irradiation to increase the Al-hole defects and finally followed by a 15 minute anneal at 300 °C, to promote hole transfer from Al-hole defects to the ODC creating E'_1 . Unfortunately, at least to our knowledge, the protocol proposed is based on a single experiment (Toyoda and Hattori, 2000) conducted on a single sample of granitic quartz. Later, although many studies reported clustering of heat-treated E'_1 values in sediments that were interpreted as a change in the source of the sediments, the initial heating recommended in the protocol, aimed at erasing the host rock initial concentration of E'_1 is not reported to be carried out (e.g., Sun et al., 2007, Wang et al., 2020) without any explanation as to why this step was omitted.

Despite this, we do concur with the idea that a heating step will result in an increase of E'_1 likely due to the hole transfer from the Al-h to the ODC. As such we have carried out heating experiments and in **Figure 4** we present the results carried out only for samples where E'_1 has reached a steady state (see section 3.1). Panel a presents the relationship between the heat treated E'_1 as function of the value of the same signal when the sample was not heated. The relationship is clearly linear for samples worldwide. The intercept is zero within error. The value of the slope is 8.7 ± 1.3 . Here the value of the slope can be regarded as having a physical meaning as the same signals are measured using the same measurement parameters. Based on the assumption that the heat treated E'_1 is an indication of the total number of oxygen vacancies, this would imply that the total number of oxygen vacancies is ~ 7 -10 times higher than the paramagnetic E'_1 defects. It is important to note that a similar conclusion was

reached by Odom (1996), namely that about 25% of oxygen vacancies are paramagnetic although the samples analysed in that study were quartz phenocrysts extracted from silicic volcanic rocks.

Figure 4. a) Geographical average of E'_1 intensity before and after heating to 350°C for 15 min. The samples and the doses used for each region are as follows: North Ukraine: STY1.10 + 2000 Gy, South Ukraine: ROX 1.9 natural, Carpathian basin: HUG natural + 2000 Gy, Lower Danube basin average of 2MV80 natural + 2000 Gy, 2MV80 natural + 5000 Gy and 2MVL3A natural + 2000 Gy, Chinese loess: average of D881-26 natural, D881-28 natural and D881-30 natural.

b) Geographical average of peroxy intensity before heating versus E'_1 intensity after heating at 350 °C for 15 min. The samples and their dosage used for each region are as follows: North Ukraine: STY 1.10 natural +2000 Gy, South Ukraine: ROX 1.9 natural, Carpathian basin: average of 2MV80 natural

+ 2000 Gy, 2MV80 natural + 5000 Gy and 2MVL3A natural + 2000 Gy, Chinese loess: average of D881-26 natural, D881-28 natural and D881-30 natural.

c) Geographical average of OSL sensitivity after heating to 350 °C for 15 min and before heating. The samples and their dosage used for each region are as follows: North Ukraine: STY 1.10 + 2000 Gy, South Ukraine: ROX 1.9 natural, Carpathian basin: HUG natural + 2000 Gy, Lower Danube basin: average of 2MV80 natural + 2000 Gy, 2MV80 natural + 5000 Gy and 2MVL3A natural + 2000 Gy, Chinese loess: average of D881 26 natural, D881 28 natural and D881 30 natural.

d) OSL sensitivity after heating the samples to 350 °C for 15 min as function of amplitude of E'_1 after heating to 350°C for 15 min. The samples and the given doses used for each region are as follows: North Ukraine: STY 1.10 + 2000 Gy, South Ukraine: ROX 1.9 natural, Carpathian basin: HUG natural + 2000 Gy, Lower Danube basin: average of 2MV80 natural + 2000 Gy, 2MV80 natural + 5000 Gy and 2MVL3A natural + 2000 Gy, Chinese loess: average of D881-26 natural, D881-28 natural and D881-30 natural.

In **figure 4 (panel b)** the heat treated E'_1 is presented as function of the amplitude of peroxy signals. As expected, the linear relationship stands, further reinforcing the idea that oxygen deficiency (either paramagnetic or diamagnetic) and oxygen excess defects are indeed created as pairs. Dave et al. (2022a), showed that during heating the amplitude of peroxy defects does not change significantly. **Figure S4** presents the spectra of the peroxy defects before and after heating while **Table S2** presents the ratio of the amplitude of the heated to the unheated signal. While there is a decrease, in general this amounts to 30%, which although not insignificant, is far less than the almost one order of magnitude increase in E'_1 by the same heating treatment. However, the change in the shape of the spectra clearly shows that the peroxy signal is an overlap of various signals that will require an in-depth characterisation in the future.

Figure 4 (panel c) presents the OSL sensitivity of the heated samples as function of the OSL sensitivity of the same samples before the heating. Except for the most sensitive sample (STY from north Ukraine), the relationship is linear with a slope of 2.7 ± 0.7 , which means that sensitivity increases about 3 times when samples are heated for 10 minutes at 300°C. If the very sensitive sample is taken into account, the dataset is better represented by a single saturation exponential function as further sensitisation may likely not be possible in the case of these already very bright samples. The relationship between the OSL sensitivity after heating and the value of the heat treated E'_1 (considered to better represent the total number of oxygen vacancies) remains, the Pearson's r correlation coefficient of 0.84 being very similar to that of 0.85 obtained in case of unheated samples.

Consequently, while the thermal treatment certainly results in better measurement precision as the values of E'_1 signals as well as the OSL sensitivity are increased it does not seem to result in either better correlation of the analysed signals or a better separation of the properties of the samples analysed, which would be a desirable outcome for provenance methods. As such, measuring the steady state (as described in section 3.1) of E'_1 and peroxy signals as well as the OSL sensitivity has a potential for provenance study that is worth pursuing.

3.5. Discussion of OSL and ESR properties in the context of U-Pb detrital zircon age distributions

In previous sections it has been shown that the OSL sensitivity is correlated to the concentration of E'_1 defects, the assumed total number of oxygen vacancies (heat treated E'_1) as well as peroxy defects and that samples from different locations worldwide can be discerned based on these signatures. Loess is windblown and transported over long distances and as such one can assume that the intrinsic characteristics of the source rocks can be distinguished over the effect of transport in the variability of the luminescence and ESR properties of sedimentary grains. As such here we tentatively compare the above-mentioned trapped charge properties and signals to crystallisation ages of the source rocks obtained very recently by others using detrital zircon U-Pb analysis. Samples from Northern Ukraine clearly stand out as having the highest OSL sensitivity as well as the highest concentration of intrinsic defects in terms of both E'_1 as well as peroxy. U-Pb detrital zircon age distributions presented for Stayky loess (Pańczyk et al., 2020) showed substantial relative probability peaks at 2.7 Ga, 1.6 Ga and 1Ga, therefore these samples contain Meso- and Paleo-Proterozoic as well as Cadomian zircons. Aleinikoff, et al. (2008) presented U-Pb detrital zircon age distributions for Nebraskan sites while for the Roxolany site in South Ukraine the same analysis was performed by Nawrocki et al., 2018. Both these sites have important age distribution components in the > 1Ga age range, their relative frequency being higher in Nebraskan loess that has the second highest OSL sensitivity. Archean grains were found in these sites (older than 2.5 Ma). Varsican zircons (320–350 Ma) alongside Danubian zircons (290–300 Ma) are the most dominant peaks for the Danube basin (Ducea et al., 2020), where Ga ages appear with a reduced frequency and sensitivity of the OSL signals in quartz from nearby loess deposits is one order of magnitude lower. The sensitivity of quartz in the Chinese Loess Plateau on which many studies have reported detrital zircon ages for the Chinese loess (e.g., Stevens et al., 2010, Zhang et al., 2016, Fenn et al., 2017, Sun et al., 2018) is similar to that of quartz in the Carpathian Basin, where the relative contribution of Ga ages is even lower as for Danube Basin (see figure 4a versus 4d and 5c respectively in Ducea et al., 2020). To further sustain our observations, we note that WIDG8, a sample

on which modern OSL dating protocols have been developed (Murray and Wintle, 2000) is generally accepted and well known in the luminescence dating community for its bright fast component signals has sandstone as a source rock, which means that the primary material has itself undergone transport. But, on the other hand, U-Pb zircon chronologies in Kimberly region where the sample originates from indicate ages around 2 Ga. (Tyler et al., 1999).

We do acknowledge that it is difficult to compare the two datasets in a quantitative manner at this stage due to the higher durability of zircon compared to quartz. As such the assumption that the relative proportion of detrital zircon modes accurately reproduces the mass balance of sediments from potential source terranes can be questioned (Moecher and Samson, 2006). Also as explained above the closure temperature of the investigated signals in quartz needs to be thoroughly studied as it remains questionable how the potential thermal history of the source rocks could have influenced the evolution of the investigated signals, making the two data sets (U-Pb detrital zircon and OSL and ESR data) not directly comparable. Finally, one should not forget that U-Pb detrital zircon age distributions are obtained on single grains while the OSL sensitivity as well as ESR data presented at this stage was obtained on multiple grains. The advantage however is that, although not trivial, trapped charge dating methods allow single grain analysis to be carried out. For OSL studies it is well known that most of the signal comes from only a few grains, typically with less than 10% of the grains contributing to over 90% of the signal. For example, for a sample collected from Roxolany site, South Ukraine, analysed here (ROX 1.14), by analysing 3800 grains we have identified 353 grains with natural OSL signals of more than 50 counts recorded in the first 0.06 s of green laser stimulation. Out of these, 44 grains (1.2% of the total measured grains) contribute to 70% of signal. Although numerically dominant, the dimmer grains only make up ~20% of the summed total signal (Anechitei-Deacu et al., 2018). A physical explanation for this range observed in single grains quartz OSL signals needs to be provided. In the context presented above, it is natural to ask whether these defects or their precursors are related to defects in quartz in the source rocks or even if that the few grains with bright OSL signal are the counterparts of the grains coming from Archean and Proterozoic rocks as reflected in U-Pb detrital zircon age distributions on the same sediments. Future studies will aim at understanding what causes this variability in OSL sensitivity and what are the defects involved that make these grains so bright compared to the others.

4. Conclusions

Most quantitative provenance studies focus on investigation of accessory minerals. In contrast the most abundant mineral in sedimentary systems, quartz remained largely unexplored. Quartz crystals contain a vast number of point defects, intrinsic or due to impurities. We showed for the first time that the laboratory and natural dose response curves of intrinsic defects, namely the E'₁ centre and then peroxy ESR signals of quartz overlap and reach a steady state for doses over about 1000 Gy. A strong linear relationship with zero intercept between E'₁ and peroxy signals for quartz from loess samples worldwide is reported, supporting the hypothesis that these defects are Frenkel pairs. Moreover, significant correlations between the OSL sensitivity and the two aforementioned ESR signals were reported, and they remained valid even after the samples were heated for E'₁ to reach its maximum value, thus clearly suggesting a relationship between OSL sensitivity and oxygen vacancies in general. While further experimental and theoretical studies are on the way to establish trapped charge dating signals and properties as provenance indicators the dataset presented here clearly shows that E'₁ and peroxy signal intensities, as well as the OSL sensitivity are significantly higher in loess from regions where the source rocks include significant components of old (Ga) ages, supporting our general hypothesis that oxygen related defects are likely created by inefficient processes such as alpha damage that occur in the long time spent by the quartz crystal in the source rocks. The presented results show that signals and properties quantifiable by the applications of trapped charge dating methods have great potential to enabling differentiating samples from different geological sources.

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SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Figure S1. Map of worldwide loess distribution modified after Li et al. (2020) provided by Yanrong Li. The investigated loess sites are indicated on the map. LC: Chinese Loess Plateau, Luochuan (Kabacińska, et al., 2022), END: Nebraska, Enders (Tecsá et al., 2020). The inset gives a close-up of the central and southeastern European loess belt and shows the investigated study sites HUG: Carpathian basin, Dunaszekcső (Újvári et al., 2014), MV: Lower Danube basin, Mircea Voda (Groza-Săcaciú et al., 2020), ROX: South Ukraine, Roxolany (Anechitei-Deacu et al., 2018), STY: North Ukraine, Stayky (Veres al., 2018).

Figure S2: Typical optically stimulated luminescence decay curve for 63-90 mm quartz from sample ROX 1.9. The signal was induced by a beta dose of 17 Gy and stimulated with blue LEDs for 40 s at 125 °C. The net signal was integrated from the first 0.308 s of stimulation (red dashed lines) and a background evaluated from 1.538 s to 2.307 s of stimulation time (green dotted lines) was subtracted.

Table S1. The Single Aliquot Regenerative dose (SAR) protocol used in this study. Bold letters indicate the step used for OSL sensitivity evaluation.

	Regenerative dose 17 Gy
Preheat 220 °C for 10 s, 5 °C/s	Preheat 220 °C for 10 s
OSL 125 °C for 40 s	OSL 125 °C for 40 s
Test dose 17 Gy	Test dose 17 Gy
Heat 180 °C for 0 s, 5 °C/s	Heat 180 °C for 0 s, 5 °C/s
OSL 125 °C for 40 s	OSL 125 °C for 40 s
OSL 280 °C for 40 s	

Figure S3: Typical ESR spectra of E' (a) and peroxy (b) centres, with indications how the signals were quantified. The signal amplitude was determined from the peak-to-peak height from $g = 2.0004$ to $g = 2.0001$ for E' signal, and from $g = 2.0090$ to $g = 2.0030$ for peroxy signal. B – induction of the magnetic field

Table S2: The ratio of the peroxy signal amplitude after/before heating for all samples available.; top-bottom amplitude was measured from $g = 2.009$ to $g = 2.003$.

Sample		ratio heated/original top-bottom
STY 1.10	nat + 2000 Gy	0.46
ROX 1.9	nat	0.58
2 MV 80	nat + 2000 Gy	0.86
2 MV 80	nat + 5000 Gy	0.75
2MVL3A	nat + 2000 Gy	0.72
HUG	nat + 2000 Gy	0.77
D881 26	nat	0.77
D881 28	nat	0.64
D881 30	nat	0.70

Figure S4: Peroxy spectra before and after heating overlaid for each sample investigated: North Ukraine – STY 1.10 + 2000Gy (a), South Ukraine – ROX 1.9, ROX 1.14 (b), Carpathian Basin – HUG + 2000Gy (c), Lower Danube Basin – 2 MV 80 + 2000Gy (d), 2 MV 80 + 5000Gy (e), 2MVL3A + 2000Gy (f), and Chinese Loess Plateau – D881 26 (g), 28 (h), 30 (i). All the spectra were averaged for 3 measurements (adjusted taking into account the small variations in microwave frequency and therefore magnetic field) and mass normalised. Here B refers to induction of the magnetic field.